

Review

Managing Tertiary Education for Socio-Economic Development and Political Freedom in Nigeria: The Internally-Generated Revenue Option

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Abstract

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This paper examines effective management of tertiary education for socio-economic development and political freedom, based on the application of internally-generated revenue option. It reveals that the development of education cost of higher educational implementation is enormous and, thus, requires other sources of revenue to meet school resources' commitments for the achievement of goal. Specifically, it espouses: Financing mode in education and higher education socio-economic development and political emancipation; challenges of higher education in Nigeria and socio-economic development and political emancipation; the case of the academic staff union and its struggle against the poor funding of higher education; the internally-generated revenue option as a reliable and supplementary source of finance of higher education; sources of school revenue generation and higher education socio-economic development and political emancipation. The paper concludes and recommends that: public-private-partnership should be employed to cater for other financial needs of higher institutions in Nigeria; and all stakeholders in the management of higher education system must employ other sources of funding like Universities' Action Researches Conduct; Capacity-building Training Programmes; Parent-University Linkage Programmes; and even Grant-manship and collaboration activities and programmes for additional internally-generated revenue.

Keywords: Higher education, Internally-generated Revenue, Political emancipation, School resources management, Socio-economic development

INTRODUCTION

Globally, it has been established that any form of educational system as a social service enterprise requires huge sum of funding for total effective and efficient operations in order to achieve goal. Education is commonly perceived as the most powerful weapon in alleviating poverty, elevating economic growth, producing skilled human resources, creating a healthy and enlightened social environment as well as creating self-

reliant and sufficient nation (Osuji and Koko, 2018). Leadership of tertiary institutions simultaneously is expected to be prudent and transparent in the spending of monies coming and going out of the system. Education draws inspiration and nourishment from society, but in turn, contributes to the growth, renewal and development of that society (Esu and Junaid, 2013). Tertiary education across the globe faces series of challenges ranging from

provisions and maintenance of instructional facilities down the road to provisions and disbursements of staff welfare/incentives for teaching and non-teaching personnel. A sharp decline in crude oil prices from 2013-2016 catapulted Nigeria into recession that added to the country's long list of challenges: the violence of Boko Haram insurgency; endemic corruption; politics among others (Salihu, 2015). The development has actually negative effect on socio-economic situation in tertiary Institutions. More than 60 per cent of Nigerian students in tertiary institutions are under the age of 24 years and there is not enough school material to cater for their academic needs within the University environment. Universities in Nigeria had no facilities to accommodate the teaming students who usually write Joint Admission Matriculation Board Exams before only but a few of them could be given admission into Federal Polytechnics, Colleges of Education, Monotechnics and similar tertiary Institutions year in year out.

According to statistics, JAMB provides on its website a total of 1,579,027 students to sit for the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination, UTME in 2016. 69.6 per cent of university applicants made it to federal University, 27.5 per cent to State University and less than 1 per cent to private University (Osipian, Ararat 2013). This shows that number of candidates then, currently exceeds the number of available universities seats by a ratio of 2:1. In 2015, only 415,500 out of 1,428, 379 applicants were admitted to the University. Furthermore, between 1980 and 2017, the number of recognized universities has grown tenfold from 16 to 152, as reported by Nigeria's National University Commission, (NUC), (Osipian, and Ararat 2013). Admission to public university in Nigeria is very competitive and based on scores in UTME and Nigeria's education entry JAMB policy was examined in competing for talents and criticism as rigorous and therefore affect the youth's talents as they find it difficult to gain entry to University (Achienuwu-Nworgu, 2009). Out of school children are more prevalent in basic schools but nowadays, Unified Tertiary Matriculation Exams has thrown so many brilliant students to be out of University. University politics has influenced the growth of the system in a negative way through bribery and corruption among the staff of higher institutions of learning.

The most pressing problems facing Nigeria's Higher education system remains the severe underfunding of its universities (Salihu, 2015). The federal government which is responsible for sustaining public universities has over the past decades not significantly increased the share of the government budget dedicated to education, despite exploding students' population. It was equally reported further that between 2003 to 2013, education spending fluctuated from 8.21 per cent of the total budget in 2003 to 6.42 per cent in 2009 and to 8.7 per cent in 2013. In 2014, the government significantly increased

education spending to 10.7 as against 26 per cent benchmark as recommended by UNESCO of the total budget but it remains to be seen if this share can be maintained following the oil price induced fiscal crisis (Salihu, 2015). In sharp contrast to the scenario, Universities requires other sources of revenue to meet school resources' commitments for the achievement of goal.

Politics and education constitute the springboard towards the development of an institutional literate citizenry for the sustainability and improvement of society through teaming students already processed to contribute their quotas for national development (Amadioha, 2018). The bane against socio-economic development and political emancipation in the growth of an institutional literate citizenry for the sustainability and improvement hence abound. Most managers of tertiary education operations are faced with the problem of sourcing for and/or management of the sourced funds as well as disbursements on human and non-human resources in the Tertiary Institution organization. Universities are expected to turn out students as products for socio-economic development and at the same time having free hands to discharge mandatory duties against the dictates of politicians who hold the leadership position in the country. In most instances, politics do influence educational practices in tertiary institutions in a positive or negative measure. There exist disunity between socio-economic development and political freedom, when it comes to issue of fund provision and disbursement to higher education (Amadioha, 2018). The discrepancies or disunity between politics and education has arisen as a result of school decisions, policies and actions taken by those in authority, which have had negative implications on stated goals of education. The ultimate aim of education is for sustainable development (UNESCO, 2011). In tertiary institutions, education is not only a right, like the right to have proper food or shelter over the citizen's head, but a passport to human and national development. The development of socio-economic and political freedom is the key towards achievement of school objectives in the long run. Education opens doors, expands opportunities and freedom to foster peace, democracy and economic growth as well as improving health and reducing poverty (Joe Project Store, 2018).

The political system contrary to the goals of education has taught the citizens, including the younger generation, powerful lessons on selfishness, tribalism, the uncontrolled lust for power and, most especially, the greed for more money at the expense of the promotion of enhanced teaching and learning processes. This development has affected management of available funds in higher education terrain. It has taught good lessons on social vices like bribery and corruption, insincerity and lack of accountability. The expectation is that there is supposed to be political emancipation in

schools and colleges for the promotion of socio-economic development. The significance of education reflects huge expenditures made by government at various levels on provision and services and the persistent cry by the public for Government to implement 26% UNESCO recommendation (Agi, 2013).

Higher education is seen as the kind of education one receives in post-secondary institutions, tertiary institutions or institutions of higher learning, owned by federal, states, and or private individuals/agencies as provided by the policy of education. According to Akinyemi and Ofem (2012), higher education in Nigeria is the education acquired after secondary education in Federal Universities, State Universities, Universities of Technology, Universities of Agriculture, Polytechniques and Colleges of Education. For several decades, African countries and their development partners have placed great emphasis on primary and, more recently, secondary education. However, they neglected tertiary education, which is the level of school meant to contribute to national development through high-level, relevant manpower training. Thus, tertiary education is aimed at facilitating national socio-economic growth, and mitigating poverty among citizenry. The Dakar Summit on Education For All in 2000, for example, advocates only for primary education as a driver of social welfare, but unfortunately left tertiary education in the background (Bloom, Canning and Chan, 2005). The aftermath of this scenario means that there is inadequate source of fund from the part of political government and administrators on the whole.

Additionally, literary education in the 4Rs (reading, writing, arithmetic and religion) dominated the missionary education which prepared recipients for emerging job opportunities, as teachers, church evangelists or pastors, clerks and interpreters in those years. While most of the missions did establish primary schools initially, very little emphasis was placed on secondary and higher education (Mkpa, 2013). Despite this, Western models of education have been the most successful in meeting the overall learning needs of Africa (Ololube, 2012). This paper, therefore, examined effective management of tertiary education for socio-economic development and political freedom, based on the application of internally-generated revenue option. It reveals the development that the cost of higher educational implementation is enormous and, thus, requires other sources of revenue to meet the need for the achievement of goal.

Financing Mode in Education and Higher Education Socio-economic Development and Political Emancipation

Financing mode refers to the means and channels through which higher education obtains or generates

revenue in meeting its enormous financial commitments/ activities and/or projects. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria in collaboration with International Labour Organisation (ILO) Action Programme on Education (2004-2005), the allocations to Education in the National Budget for 2003, 2004 and 2005 were 7%, 12% and 11%, respectively. These did not include the Universal Basic Education (UBE) and Education Trust Fund (ETF) budget allocations. The National Budget proposal for 2006 is 11%, which does not include the UBE and ETF budget provisions. The quantum of the Private Sector contribution is, however, unknown. The expected best practice today requires public-private-partnership in finance provisions while managing all levels of educational institutions. Based on this assertion, there was no specific reference to how much should be allocated to higher education in the country at a particular period. Undoubtedly, the mode from 2003, 2004, 2005 and 2006 fund allocations directly affected fund provisions and disbursements on higher education projects. The justification to suit balance financial disbursement to tertiary education system call for re-think and fresh policy strand on higher education in the light of the present formula for fund allocation to the system and re-structuring pattern as well as mode of internally-generated revenue.

Challenges of finance on Higher Educational Material resources

The submissions on obstacles to sound financial bases for education and sound distribution of resources in institutions of higher learning on teaching and learning support functions are in line with the Federal Republic of Nigeria in collaboration with International Labour Organisation (ILO) Action Programme on Education (2004-2005).

- i) inconsistent financial policy and late or non-release of budget allocation;
- ii) the Nation's over dependence on oil income, which is unstable and affects budgetary allocation to the education sector;
- iii) under-funding of the education sector;
- iv) inadequate data on the education sector; and
- v) misapplication of funds allocated to the education sector.

Items (i) - (v) in application to higher education management serve as obstacles that affect the four levels of educational systems in Nigeria, namely: i) Early childhood (pre-primary); ii) Basic Education (9 years) - comprising Primary and Junior Secondary Education, which is compulsory, universal and free; iii) Senior Secondary Education (3 years); and specifically iv) Tertiary Education. The systems are specially expected to be taken care of, for the laudable attainment of goals

as contained in the National Policy on Education.

The Goals of Higher Institutions

In line with the Federal Republic of Nigeria, (FRN:2014), the goals of tertiary education are as follows:

- i. To contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training;
- ii. To develop and inculcate values for the survival of the individual and society;
- iii. To develop the individual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate the local and external environments;
- iv. To acquire both physical and intellectual skills, which will enable the individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society;
- v. To promote and encourage scholarship and community service;
- vi. To promote and cement national unity; and
- vii. To promote national and international understanding and interaction.

Challenge of Higher Education in Nigeria and Socio-economic Development and Political Emancipation

The level at which students seek admission into the higher institutions is basically on the high side, which requires increase in the players' fund commitment till present. Pemedede (2007) postulated, however, that underfunding has made staff and students offered appointment and admission, respectively not to have access to the latest books and journals. The laboratories lack basic equipment, so experiments cannot be conducted and local research funds have virtually dried up. This has posed serious threat to the managers of higher education and made them to take more students into the system, thus leaving students' population on the increase beyond geometric rate. Higher schools of learning at any rate are all aimed at producing knowledgeable and competent work force for proactive national development (Ololube, 2013). The human capital building of projected competent work force is expected to be developed. TETFund had been making visible impact on supporting tertiary education in terms of sponsoring academic staff in Nigerian universities for higher degrees, conferences, workshops and valuable research endeavours (ASUU, 2013). This development is questionable when it comes to practical implementation in the system. Moreso, instructional facilities to cater for the number of enrolment are grossly inadequate and that led to other advanced issue of high lecturers-students' ratio. In most cases, there are feasible challenges of limited lecture halls, teaching materials and even shortage of academic staff provision in the tertiary

institutions. The imbalance was corroborated by Akinyemi and Ofem (2012), who stated that increase in enrolment of students' yearly; inadequate fiscal resources against qualitative education and the needed national development are the order of the day in such institutions. According to Ekundayo and Ajayi (2009); Ekpenyong (2010); Uriah and Wosu (2012), higher education is generally accepted as a major instrument for the promotion of socio-economic, political and cultural developments. Notwithstanding this assertion, poor socio-economic development in schools of higher learning adversely affects the infrastructural facilities, timely and adequate payment of salaries and allowances of staff among others addresses. It clearly shows that money resources have to be provided in the right proportion in order to meet the financial needs of higher education on human and non-human resources. The political classes are very good in rationalization of financial resources in the implementation of education programmes over the years due to the apparent scarcity of resources, needed to cater for the expenses of higher education. Justification for their approach is not far-fetched because of the complexities of information technology, population explosion, and increase in government expenditure on other sectors of the national economy that prompted limited education resources to higher education. Unfortunately, these factors have hitherto contributed to the failure to meet the benchmark of United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization of 26 percent of the national budget on the education sector of Nigeria economy (Ekpo, 2014).

The specific Challenge of Political/Legal Obstacles

The existing political/legal framework exerts a great deal of influence and control over education in Nigeria. This framework involves both political and legal stability, which include legislation, policies, and the rules and regulations guiding the establishment of institutions of higher education (Ololube, 2013). All these factors put together will basically affect funding of higher institutions. Since Nigeria's independence in October 1960, political instability has been the order of the day. Higher education reforms started by one administration are brutally interrupted by the next and the differences between federal and state government's higher education policies can also be quite challenging. Neither the military nor the civilian regimes have paid particular attention to the higher education development of Nigeria (Ololube, 2013). The constant stand-off between the Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC), Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), Academic Staff Union of Polytechnics (ASUP) and their counterpart in the Colleges of Education has contributed to failures in the implementation of higher education agenda as the

aggrieved parties fail to reach consensus on the way forward. The bone of contention here is on discrepancies on finance to fund all these institutions of higher learning. Funding of human and non-material resources of course matters. The principles of collective bargaining are no longer respected as harsh words and the imposition of orders by the stronger onto the weaker persists (Ololube, 2013).

The Case of the Academic Staff Union and Funding of Higher Education

All efforts of ASUU to promote better learning in the system over the years in their struggles have been focused on ensuring that the political leadership in the nation takes care of fund provisions and disbursement to cater for the financial needs of universities' projects. For instance, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund), formerly known as Education Trust Fund (ETF), which is saddled with the responsibility of providing funds for the provision and upgrading of teaching and learning facilities as well as training of University staff is a brain child of ASUU (Uzoh, 2017). There are other struggles of sourcing for universities' autonomous funding as championed by ASUU in Universities in Nigeria. TETFund has been making visible impact in supporting tertiary education in terms of sponsoring academic staff in Nigerian universities for higher degrees, and sponsoring conferences, workshops and valuable research endeavours (ASUU, 2013). Basically, there is limited performance from the part of ASUU regarding this due to the negative influence of political on tertiary education.

The Needs' Assessment Fund that is also currently used in setting up structures, providing teaching and learning facilities and training of academic staff of Nigerian Universities is a fall-out of the 2013 ASUU strike that lasted for six months (Uzoh, 2017). Sincerely, ASUU is a fearsome Union in Nigeria as of now who has always take it upon its own shoulder to fight for the tertiary education industry. The recent struggle of ASUU strike in year 2020 lasted for almost ten months of hunger for teaming members. Generally, education is poorly funded at all levels in Nigeria, and this factor explains the decaying level of the educational system in the country. This, in the long run, has led adverse effect on nation, staff and students' socio-economic development in schools of higher learning, there abound inadequate or non-supply of infrastructural facilities, salary and allowances' of staff not paid, among others. The development in the system ought to address the need to provide money resources in the right proportion in order to meet the financial commitments of higher education towards human and non-human resources. Therefore,

the struggle continues between the Federal Government of Nigeria and ASUU. The struggle may be reduced to its barest minimum if all higher institution managers of education would look elsewhere to source for more avenues to generate funds in order to meet up with the varying financial needs in the system.

The Internally-generated Revenue Option and Finance of Higher Education

Higher education funding strategies come from different sources. It is sad to note that all sources from the federal, state, local government levels and other notable avenues are bedeviled with the problem of inadequacy of fund generation and disbursement. This fact has negatively affected the varieties of school resources due to general challenge of socio-economic and political emancipations facing the Institutions of higher learning. A reliable and sufficient funding platform is a necessity for achieving access to an excellence in university education in Africa (Faboyede, Faboyede, and Fakile, 2017). Faboyede *et al.* (2017) further reported that sources and systems of fund for Nigerian universities have proven inadequate below the benchmark recommended by UNESCO and various demands of ASUU in these tertiary institutions and which now calls for alternative funding mechanism has become very important more than ever before. The Federal Government of Nigeria has been investing less than two per cent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on higher education in the last 10 years; thus, spending 1.6 per cent on University education (Faboyede, Faboyede and Fakile, 2014).

Akinyemi, Ofem, Adebisi and Deji-Folutile (2012) confirmed that funding allocation to higher education has failed to deliver quality education service delivery, hence the need to re-calibrate the funding model scheme to guarantee making the higher education system more nationally relevant and globally competitive. They reported further that the political social and economic factors, which are currently and significantly impacting on the world economy have necessitated the diversification of the sources of education funding, mainly because of reliance on only exclusive formal way of revenue generation outside that of internally-generated revenue (Faboyede, Faboyede and Fakile, 2014). Supporting this scenario, most universities were grossly understaffed; laboratories and workshops were old with inappropriate furnishing; classrooms/lecture rooms were overcrowded and overstressed; equipment and consumables were absent; higher students'/lecturers' ratio as high as 1:500 as far back as 2012, *vide* Federal Government Survey Need Assessment of the university system research result.

Sources of School Revenue Generation and Higher Education Socio-economic Development and Political Emancipation

There exist a well-established fact that money is an essential tool in higher education for socio-economic development and to attain political freedom for implementing various school plans and programmes. According to Horne (2002), strategic financial planning involves analyzing the financial flow of an organization, forecasting the consequences of various investment, financing and dividend decisions, and weighing the effects of various alternatives. This is the development in profit-oriented financial planning which could work for school organizations, including higher education in bringing diversification of internally generated revenue. The advantage of financial planning is that it forces management to take account of possible deviations from the organization's anticipated path.

A financial strategy will usually address five key issues namely: the long-term viability of the organization and matching resources with objectives; maintaining productive capacity to meet current objectives; financing development and investment; the evaluation of strategic alternatives and managing risks; and integrating financial and other corporate strategies. This strategy may be feasible by exploring government sources of fund allocation and then adding the internally-generated sources of funding to the existing ones (Amanze and Nwosu, 2016). External entrepreneurship in institutions of higher learning system could be termed to mean internally-generated revenue. It refers to the first phenomenon that consists of the process of combining resources dispersed in the environment by individual entrepreneurs with their unique resources to create a new resource combination, independent of all others through external efforts entailing mergers, joint ventures, corporate venture, venture nurturing, venture spin-off and others (Gautam, and Verma, 2002).

Adequate tertiary education financial planning will cater for staff salaries; for putting physical school plants and facilities like buildings, laboratories, classrooms, staff quarters, purchase of materials for repairs and maintenance. Thus, financial management becomes imperative, especially with inadequate funding, rising cost of education materials, inflation and other complexities. Most Universities' managers, administrators and planners are usually affected by their ignorance on the need to look outside of the box to generate revenue to meet all expenses required on both human and material resources. It has been established that shortage of fund for tertiary education plans and programmes will pose serious threats to the realization of overall national and international socio-economic and political developments on education (Adesokan and Egbebi, 2010).

Institutions of Higher learning could generate revenue from the following sources as opined by Adesokan and Egbebi (2010):

- i. Allocation from government provision through the budget to different levels of government by the National Economic Advisory Committee for disbursement to education sector of higher institutions
- ii. Donations and gifts from philanthropists; multinational corporations like Mobile Telecommunication Network (MTN), Global Communication (GLO), international development partners like United Nations Development Projects (UNDP), United Nations International Children Education Fund (UNICEF), World Health Organization (WHO), World Bank Group.
- iii. Fees and levies.
- iv. Universities' action research proceeds.
- v. Training programmes.
- vi. Parent-University linkage programmes.
- vii. Water production business; dairy farm; mini-refinery of crude-oil like Ahmadu Bello University Engineering studying are doing and many more.
- ix. Grant-manship and collaboration activities and programmes.

CONCLUSION

The paper explored factors that surround management of Institutions of higher learning resources outside of the statutory sources of funding. The crisis of falling in the price of crude oil, corruption of high order in and outside of the University environment due to negative influence of politics on education, insecurity challenges of Boko Haram insurgency, over population of students seeking admission into the tertiary institutions, non-challant attitude of tertiary institution leadership to explore other plausible avenues to generate revenue aside of government allocation and a host of others imbroglio contributed immensely to inadequate socio-economic development and political freedom in the system, It examines the conventional sources of funding to meet universities' laudable objectives in addition to other sources of funding as treated in the content of the discourse. The government has for long focused its attention of funding of education on primary and secondary education systems, and specifically not concentrated sufficiently enough on higher education system. Activities of corrupt politician, junior and management employees of tertiary Institutions has equally done a serious damage to the sector of the economy. In order for managing tertiary education for socio-economic development and political freedom for the attainment of universities' goals as stipulated in the policy, adequate provisions and disbursement of funds are expected to be effectively and efficiently organized

by managers, planners and administrators of respective higher institutions. Relevant sources of revenue generation which could be employed include donations, tuition fees, research products and business ventures.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper recommends as follows:

Public-private-partnership should be employed to cater for other financial needs of higher institutions in Nigeria. As private organisations disburse funds to help Institutions of higher learning, they should simultaneously demand for the proper accountability as they participate in the management of such tertiary Institutions

All stakeholders in the management of higher education system must begin to think outside of the box; by employing other sources of funding like Universities' action research implementation; training programmes; parent-University linkage programmes; and even grant-manship and collaboration activities and programmes for additional internally-generated revenue.

Fund managers in the higher education system should employ committee system in the disbursement of funds on various higher education projects to ensure transparency. The account of all incomes and expenditures should be published periodically for the consumption of both tertiary education community and the outside world.

Political leaders should provide more fund supplies to higher education programmes and projects as done for both primary and even secondary school systems. An institution like

TETFund/ETF and Universal Basic Education Commission should be re-directed to concentrate and disburse more fund to higher education system. Political emancipation for socio-economic development for advancement of higher education will result.

Provisions and maintenance of existing instructional facilities down the road to provisions and disbursements of staff welfare/incentives for teaching and non-teaching personnel have to be taken care of, by both internal and external stakeholders.

There should be committee in charge of continuous maintenance of higher education system instructional and learning facilities to adequately cater for provision, usage and maintenance of school material resources.

All obstacles to sound financial bases for education and sound distribution of resources to teaching and learning support functions should be revisited and necessary solutions provided by respective stakeholders. Information and telecommunication technology software should be provided for proper accountability in Universities by that application of forensic accounting.

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